

Women's Role in Inclusive and Sustainable Economic Growth and Gender Equity in Indian Agriculture: Vision 2047

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Abstract:

In India, the agriculture sector dominates employment, with a 46.1 per cent share in 2023-24. Notably, the share of women in agriculture employment workforce is around 64.4 percent, underscoring the critical role of women and their contribution in ensuring food and nutrition security and supporting household income and impact on the agricultural economy. This paper examine vital role of women in Indian Agriculture and their contribution to inclusive and sustainable economic development. It reviews existing government policies and highlights the structural barriers to gender equity. The paper proposes an equitable approach for women's empowerment and gender justice aligned with the global sustainable development goals in the vision of Viksit Bharat by 2047.

Keywords: *Women's role in agriculture, Gender equity, feminization of agriculture, women's contribution to agriculture, women empowerment*

Introduction:

Recently, the United Nations declared 2026 the International Year of Women Farmers to raise awareness of the crucial roles women play across agricultural food systems, from production to trade, and promote actions to close the gender gaps and improve women's livelihoods worldwide. And underscore that Women farmers are central to food security, nutrition, and economic resilience. At the global level, women make up a significant share of the world agriculture workforce and play a central role in household food security and nutrition. and supporting Sustainable Development Goal SDG 1, No Poverty; SDG 2, Zero Hunger; SDG 5, gender equality; SDG 8, decent work and economic growth, and SDG 10, Reduce Inequalities. In 2021 at global level, 40 percent of women workers were engaged in agriculture food system, equal to men. In India, the agriculture sector employs 46.1 percent workforce in 2023-24. share of women workforce make up to 64.4

per cent in 2023-24. Underscore women are vital in agriculture productive activities.(NSO, 2025; UN Women, 2025) However, women's roles and contributions remain undervalued and unrecognized. women faces issues at both levels. At the domestic level, women often serve as unpaid family workers. And at the farm level, working conditions are irregular, informal, part-time, low-paid or unpaid work, and labour-intensive, hence women are more vulnerable human assets. They continue to face systemic barriers, including limited access to land ownership, credit, technologies, education, extension services, and participation in decision-making at all levels, hindering agricultural productivity and inclusive growth. (Tutej, 2000 ;Panda et al., 2025)

The paper aims to analyse women's role and contribution in Inclusive and sustainable economic growth and gender Equity in Indian Agriculture in the vision of 'Vikshit Bharat' by 2027. In this light research paper seeks answer the

following research questions: 1. How do women contribute to inclusive and sustainable agriculture growth? 2. What are the barriers faced by women in achieving gender equity in agriculture? 3 What policy approach are necessary for women farmer in Viksit Bharat Vision 2047?

Literature Review:

(Aayushi et al., 2024) studied the contribution of women in the agriculture sector and highlights the significant role played by Indian women in socio-economic development and supporting family income through farming activities. The study concluded that women's participation in farming activities is crucial for rural development and gender empowerment.

(Her Circle NGO, 2025) examined the critical role of women in Indian agriculture. The study emphasizes their contribution to food security and the rural economy. According to a study, women prefer to engage in sustainable farming practices, which highlights their role in environmental conservation and biodiversity preservation. However, women face socio-economic barriers that place them in vulnerable conditions. The study emphasises that empowerment of women in agriculture demands a comprehensive, equitable approach by providing agriculture education, financial and legal rights, and resources. The study concludes that women's participation in agriculture is crucial for food security, environmental sustainability, and rural development.

Various studies have recognised the role played by women in agricultural activities and their contribution to food security, crop cultivation, preserving seeds, livestock, environmental protection, supporting household income, and rural and sustainable agriculture development. These studies also underscored the various barriers and disabilities faced by women in agricultural farm activities and highlighted

policy reforms in rural women's empowerment. However, these reforms seem not align with long term vision of sustainable development goals and Indian long term vision of Viksit Bharat. The paper proposes an equitable approach for women's empowerment and gender justice aligned with the global sustainable development goals in the vision of Viksit Bharat by 2047.

Objectives of Research:

1. To examine the contribution to inclusive and sustainable agriculture growth in India
2. To study what are the barriers faced by women in achieving gender equity in agriculture
3. To provide a literature base for further study and policy approach are necessary for women farmer in Viksit Bharat Vision 2047?

Research Methodology:

The study is analytical in nature and is based on secondary data. Data is collected from various reputed sources, including government reports, NSO, NITI Aayog, UN Women, UNDP, FAO, research papers, and data various websites.

Women's Contribution to Indian Agriculture:

Source: Author self

i. Economic Contribution: The agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy, playing a crucial role in national income and employment. The Agricultural sector supports about 46.1

percent of the population.(Ministry of Finance GOI, 2025). Women play a crucial role in agricultural activities; the share of working women in agriculture employment is stand around 64.4 percent in 2023-24 (PLFS, 2025). Women contribute to food security and economic security, with many women acting as breadwinner in their households and supporting rural economy and contributing to reducing poverty.(Sidh & Basu, 2011).Women's role Farmer Producer Organizations (FPOs) empower rural women, promote gender equity, and enhance their economic independence, ultimately fostering sustainable agricultural and rural development.

ii. Social Contribution: Agriculture is a way of life in rural India. and women are backbone of agrarian economy. They form two third of agricultural workforce hence their role in farming activities is vital. Various studies have underscored their contribution in preserving agrobiodiversity, and regarded as true custodians of agrobiodiversity. Women's decision in selecting, conserving, and sharing seeds suited to local soils and climates. Their knowledge of indigenous crop varieties, wild edibles, and medicinal plants sustains food diversity and resilience. Women's decisions on what to plant and preserve are guided not just by yield, but by taste, aroma, ritual value, and household needs - ensuring that biodiversity flourishes in both the field and the kitchen. ([Women Farmers: Custodians of agri heritage and agrobiodiversity](#))

iii. Environmental Contribution: Research suggests that women, including those in indigenous communities, can play a crucial role in environmental preservation. This is often achieved through their traditional knowledge and agricultural methods, which have been developed and refined over generations (Singh et al., 2023) Women play crucial roles in agriculture, managing various tasks from livestock to crop cultivation, that empowering women in

agriculture is crucial for achieving gender equality, reducing poverty, and achieving sustainable development goals.(L G & N, 2024)

Challenges and Barriers:

Despite the vital role of women in farm activities, women are subject to various burdens and disabilities, as underscored by various studies. In India, the agriculture sector plays a dominant role in employment, with its share of 46.1 per cent in 2023-24. share of working women rising in agriculture employment, from 57.0 per cent in 2017-18 to 64.4 per cent in 2023-24; however, men's participation in agriculture decreased from 40.2 per cent to 36.3 per cent.(PLFS, 2025) As a result of agricultural crises, rural men had to seek other livelihood opportunities, causing them to migrate to urban areas in search of jobs, leaving women to do agricultural work, leading to the increasing feminization of agriculture. (MOSPI, 2025; Shukla et al., 2022; Mahendra Dev, 2012; Nair & Eapen, 2015; Padmaja et al., 2015). feminization in India is largely driven by out migration of men from rural areas.

However, increasing women's engagement in agricultural activities, it does not correlate with their socio-economic empowerment. Instead, this increasing trend is linked to poverty and may worsen the burden faced by rural women. And rural agriculture can be described as "feminization of agrarian distress " instead of "feminization of agriculture. (Pattnaik et al., 2018) Women face significant barriers such as limited access to productive resources, which hampers their productivity and recognition as active contributors (Subathra et al., 2021).According to Agriculture Census 2015-16, the percentage share of female operational holders is just 13.96% in 2015-16. The worse case is regarding SC and ST female grope, the share of female operational holders belonging to

SC and ST social group were estimated at 11.4% and 7.9 % respectively (Min. of Agri. GOI, 2016). Recent FAO reports underscore the scale of gender inequality and the disproportionate climate risks faced by women. The reports highlight the structural barriers limiting women's productivity, income, access to resources, and resilience. Reducing gender disparities in employment, education, and income could eliminate 52 percent of the food insecurity gap which is consistently higher among women. The unpaid care work performed by women and girls contributes at least \$ 10.8 trillion to the global economy annually.

Road map for gender empowerment and gender equity in agriculture:

Approach to gender justice and equity can be achieved through following the 'RVM trinity approach'

1. Recognition 2. Valuing 3. Empowering. This approach is interlinked to each other and supports and promotes a virtuous circle of gender and social justice.

Figure. 2: 'RVM trinity approach'

1. Recognition 2. Valuing 3. Empowering

Source: Author self

1. Recognition of women as farmers: Roadmap for gender equity in agriculture starts with defining the women farmers. According to the United Nations, "Women farmers work in diverse roles across agrifood systems and come from all backgrounds: young and older women,

Indigenous women, women in local communities, women with disabilities, and refugee and displaced women. They are smallholder producers, peasants, agricultural labourers, fishers and fish workers, beekeepers, pastoralists, processors, traders, women in agricultural sciences, rural entrepreneurs, traditional knowledge holders, and more—whether in formal or informal work, with or without land ownership." ([Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations](#)) However, in the Indian context the definition of an Indian woman farmer is not given. Defining who a woman farmer is can help agencies and governments to formulate new policies that include equity and general justice. It is now important to examine gender norms that affect the recognition of women as legitimate farmers. UN declared 2026 International Year of the Woman Farmer 2026 to accelerate gender equality and women's empowerment in agrifood systems. To define who is a woman farmer is, understanding the status of women is crucial. According to UN women recognition of the status of women starts with gender equity. UN Women organisation highlights that "Gender equality is not only a basic human right, but its achievement has enormous socio-economic ramifications. Empowering women fuels thriving economies, spurring productivity and growth. ([About UN Women | UN Women – Headquarters](#))

2. Valuing economic and social rights of women: Another crucial aspect of gender equity is valuing unpaid work and the economic and social rights of women. In India, when calculating national income, the government does not calculate the unpaid contributions made by women at the household and farm level activities. This is against the principle of natural justice by equal pay for equal work. Women often are paid less or are unpaid for their valuable contributions to farm-level activities. There is a need gender

based reforms to give women equal rights to economic resources; ownership and control over land, property, credit, technology, and natural resources. Women's integration in agricultural value chains and valuing their role and contribution entails gender equity.

3. Empowering Women: UN Women defines 'economic empowerment as a transformative, collective process through which economic systems become just, equitable and prosperous, and through which all women enjoy their economic and social rights, exercise agency and power in ways that challenge inequalities and level the playing field and gain equal rights and access to ownership of and control over resources, assets, income, time and their own lives.' (UN Women, 2024). Women's empowerment is, therefore, a dynamic, multi-dimensional process, which enables women to realise and execute their potential and powers in all spheres of life. (Anirban Mukherjee et al., 2020). Economic and social transformation of society in favour of gender equity must align with global sustainable development goals, Gender mainstreaming in NITI Aayog's Viksit Bharat vision, and national priorities

However, this approach of gender justice equity must be supported by monitoring and evaluation at local, national, and international levels. Data and statistics are vital for devising evidence-based policies and programmes on gender equality and women's empowerment.

Conclusion:

Women are Central to Inclusive and sustainable agriculture and rural development. An Indian vision of a developed India by 2047 cannot be possible without gender equitable, resilient, and inclusive policy reforms and gender sensitive approach. Institutional mechanisms, gender statistics, and data are essential for future courses of empowerment of women in agriculture. Indian

agriculture must align gender equity with sustainable development goal. The United Nations already declared 2026 as the International Year of Women Farmers to get more vision of women's contributions in this field. We need to devise new policy reforms and a strategy for this.

The paper suggests a new, broad approach to gender justice in the agriculture sector. Future research should focus on the impact of climate change on gender equity, as India is one of the 6 most vulnerable countries in the world, warned by climate risk Index, 2025. The FAO report also underscored women farmers' vulnerability due to climate extremes. The study concludes that Women play a crucial role in agriculture and participate in diverse farm activities. The study suggest RVM trinity approach: Recognition, Valuing, and Empowering women in the agricultural sector. Recognition of women as a farmer help to value their role in agricultural productivity and rural development. Valuing their contribution entails the right to productive resources, including access and ownership of land, credit, decision making, and finally social and economic independence, which in turn leads to gender equity and women's empowerment.

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